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RELEVANT ISSUES IN TEACHING INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: *This article highlights the current issues of teaching informatics and information technologies to primary school students and its role and importance today.*

Keywords: *informatics and information technologies, intellectual and cultural potential, "Smart School" program, "Electronic Diary" unified system, virtual educational tools, basic computer skills, digital literacy, Internet security, integration process.*

As in many other countries, Uzbekistan faces significant challenges in teaching primary school students the fundamentals of informatics and information technologies. Addressing these challenges is critical for ensuring effective education and preparing students to meet the demands of the digital age. As noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, mastering digital knowledge and modern information technologies is a necessary and mandatory condition for achieving progress. This will enable us to follow the most direct path toward development. We must not overlook the decisive importance of intellectual and cultural potential in nurturing unique talents and unlocking their rare abilities.

On August 22, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued Decree No. UP-357 "On Measures to Advance the Field of Information and Communication Technologies to a New Stage of Development in 2022-2023." This decree places special emphasis on schoolchildren and outlines the following priority tasks:

1. Development of the "Smart School" program aimed at monitoring students in general education schools.
2. Establishment of a special award from the regional governor for girls participating in informatics subject olympiads among students of general education schools.
3. Provision of educational institutions with necessary computer equipment, taking into account the implementation of a unified "Electronic Diary" system in general education schools.

Currently, the following key issues should be highlighted in the teaching of informatics and information technologies:

Firstly, the use of infrastructure and technology: one of the main challenges is ensuring that schools have the necessary infrastructure and technologies. Many schools, especially in rural areas, may face a shortage of computers, internet access, and other resources required for effective informatics education.

In general education schools, it is advisable to implement new forms of learning with the organization of additional classes. This will foster students' interest and need for a deep and thorough understanding of the fundamentals of informatics, allow them to apply acquired

knowledge in practice, develop professional skills, as well as teach them how to search for, acquire, and process information using the Internet.

Secondly, teacher professional development: For effective teaching of informatics and information technologies, teachers need to undergo specialized training and professional development. In many cases, teachers may lack the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate technology into the learning process.

Like any other subject, informatics and information technologies occupy a special place in the educational system, playing a crucial role in shaping students' worldview. Mastering this subject is closely related to the study of innovative technologies and their application in various fields.

Research conducted on the development of textbooks and teaching aids for informatics, as well as improving the effectiveness of their use, shows that students' mastery of the subject largely depends on practical activities. In this regard, virtual learning tools and electronic textbooks are of particular importance for the comprehensive acquisition of knowledge and skills.

Thirdly, curriculum development: It is crucial to create an age-appropriate curriculum for teaching informatics to primary school students. The curriculum should cover essential computer skills, digital literacy, and internet safety.

It is worth noting that by the order of the Minister of Preschool and School Education No. 125, dated May 15, 2023, "On Approval of the Basic Curriculum for General Education Schools for the 2023/2024 Academic Year," the Republican Educational Center was tasked with developing corresponding calendar-thematic plans based on the basic curriculum within a month. Additionally, within a week, the Ministry was to be presented with proposals for the implementation of teaching methods for informatics and information technologies in the 1st grade, the curriculum, state educational standards, and calendar-thematic plans.

Fourthly, pedagogy and teaching methods: Teaching informatics to younger students requires an innovative and engaging pedagogical approach. Teachers should use interactive and practical lessons to captivate and motivate students.

The following didactic systems can be employed in teaching informatics:

- Teaching with the use of traditional technical means;
- The "one student – several students" system;
- Organization of work in small groups;
- Use of automated classrooms;
- Programmed learning;
- Computer-based learning.

Fifthly, assessment: It is important to develop appropriate methods for evaluating students' understanding and skills in the field of informatics. Traditional assessment methods may not be suitable for testing technology skills and digital literacy.

There are various mechanisms for formative assessment that can be used in any classroom. Some of the most popular include:

1. Direct questioning or homework assignments;
2. Response journals during the learning process or tasks completed in class;
3. Tests during the lesson;
4. Graphic organizers or observing students' activity in class;
5. Feedback;
6. Self-assessment by students;
7. Adjustments to the educational process based on results.

Informatics teachers must explain to parents the importance of their children's mastery of information and communication technologies. Throughout their pedagogical activities, informatics teachers should consistently collaborate with parents. They are required to regularly provide parents with information about students' preparedness for lessons, their knowledge level, and academic performance. Additionally, informatics teachers should regularly highlight students' practical activities in informatics, their interest in the subject, and achievements in dedicated Telegram channels created for parents.

In conclusion, to ensure the effective mastery of informatics and information technologies by primary school children, collaboration between policymakers, teachers, parents, and the community is essential.

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